

THE POSITIVE TRANSFORMATION OF MULTICULTURALISM INTO STATE POLICY IN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN, HISTORICALLY POSSESSING MULTICULTURAL AND TOLERANT VALUES, AS COMPARED WITH THE INTERNATIONAL WORLD**Abbasova Y.***Head Teacher**Azerbaijan University of Languages**Department of Foreign Languages Within Faculty of Education**Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17583053>**Abstract**

When examining history, it becomes apparent that the Republic of Azerbaijan has been notably a "highly cultured" state in a positive sense. When referring to "multicultural," the concept primarily encompasses ethnic, racial, religious, and cultural diversities, along with the significant values that constitute the basis of this diversity. The term 'multiculturalism' is synonymous with the concept of multiculturalism and is closely related to the idea of tolerance as well [1].

Multiculturalism, concerning the relationship with national minorities or smaller ethnic groups, inherently reflects a fully tolerant approach to their national customs, traditions, values, language, religion and culture [1].

Multiculturalism is the coexistence of multiple cultures. The word is used in sociology, in political philosophy, and colloquially. In sociology and everyday usage, it is usually a synonym for ethnic or cultural pluralism [2] in which various ethnic and cultural groups exist in a single society. It can describe a mixed ethnic community area where multiple cultural traditions exist or a single country. Groups associated with an indigenous, aboriginal or autochthonous ethnic group and settler-descended ethnic groups are often the focus [6, p.77].

One of the positive aspects related to human beings and their qualities is the principle of mutual understanding. This implies an absolute necessity for mutual understanding in the relations between ethnic groups or national minorities and representatives of other nations residing in the country or homeland. Throughout history, the Azerbaijani people have lived by this noble practice, leaving a positive mark historically and continuing to do so presently. In essence, Azerbaijan's possession of multiculturalism, multicultural traditions, and tolerant values stems from ancient times and persists in the modern era. Azerbaijan, known as the 'Land of Fires,' has historically been a splendid place where people speaking different languages, adhering to diverse customs, religions, and spiritual values, coexist peacefully and harmoniously. As we noted, this historical trend of multicultural and tolerant values dates back to ancient times [2].

As a Land of Fires reflecting multicultural, tolerant values within itself, Azerbaijan, since ancient times, has been a beautiful place where people of various languages, diverse customs and traditions, different religious beliefs, and various spiritual values coexist peacefully, in a serene environment, fostering mutual friendship and living together in peace. As noted, the historical roots of these multicultural values are profound, stretching back to ancient times [2].

Even the ancient Azerbaijani epic tale "Kitabi-Dede Qorqud", which belongs to the 6th-7th centuries, showcases the tolerant and multicultural traditions

rooted deeply in our nation's history, revealing how humanist and esteemed our people are. Epic tales of heroism and bravery from ancient times often prominently feature multiculturalism and the presence of multicultural traditions in their narratives, notably in the story of "Qanlı Qoca oğlu Qanturalı". Regardless of religious belief or national affiliation, this tale demonstrates that the people of the Oghuz land showed no distinction towards those of different religions or languages, embracing a humanist way of life and thought" [7, p.352].

As we know, the renowned and prominent Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi lived and created during the 12th century. Upon a profound examination of the works of this gifted poet, it becomes evident that many of these works' characters embody multicultural states of being, clearly showcasing their existence. Among the remarkable poet's works, the poem "Seven Beauties" stands out in this regard—it is one of the works where multicultural traditions have a more prominent presence [3].

Discussion

Generally, the presence of a tolerant, multicultural atmosphere, multicultural traditions, and multiculturalism itself is vivid and evident in both oral and written literature from our past to the present day. Even in the works of classic Azerbaijani poets who lived and created during the medieval period, explicit references to multicultural traditions, multicultural values, and a multicultural ambiance are observed. Classical Azerbaijani poets who lived and created in the Middle Ages include Shah Ismail Khatai, Essa Tabrizi, Imadaddin Nasimi, and Muhammad Fizuli. Works of these classical Azerbaijani poets often vividly showcase tolerant examples and multicultural ideals. As we can see, the historical traditions of multiculturalism in Azerbaijan, valuing multicultural and tolerant ideals, date back to ancient times. The prioritization of preserving Zoroastrian, Christian, and Islamic monuments within the territory of Azerbaijan as one of the foremost issues aimed at safeguarding the historical heritage, multicultural, and tolerant values and ideas of Azerbaijani multiculturalism [7, p.352].

From ancient times until today, people of different faiths and languages have lived together in peace and security in Azerbaijan.

After Islam, churches representing all three branches of Christianity (Orthodox, Catholic, and Protestant) are active in the country.

Generally, when we compare the Azerbaijani people with the peoples of other countries around the world, it's clear that this nation stands out distinctly with its unique, refined, and commendable characteristics. Their distinct moral values, original culture, and even their unique talent and ability make them a shining example of a beautiful people.

Our country, the Land of Fires Azerbaijan, is a land characterized by its ethnographic diversity and favorable geographical setting, blessed with rich natural surroundings. In this country with its favorable geographical conditions and abundant nature, alongside Azerbaijani Turks, various ethnic groups such as Kurds, Talysh, Mountain Jews, Molokans, Ingiloys, Avars, Sakhurs, Lezgins, Khinalugs, Budugs, Crimean Tatars, Tats, Udins, and other minorities have lived historically and continue to live today. The Azerbaijani land has historically been an area where ethnic groups and national minorities coexist in peace and security, a territory where diverse and vibrant cultures flourish and blossom side by side [8].

These communities, belonging to ethnic minorities living on Azerbaijani soil, encompass Iranian-speaking, Turkic-speaking, and Caucasian-speaking groups. Some of these minority populations have been an integral part of Azerbaijan's population for a long time, while others have settled within the country due to various historical political events at different stages of history [7].

There are also Jewish communities (*they represent the allocton group - which generally refers to groups of people who are not indigenous to a particular area but have migrated or settled there over time*) considered among the national minorities. Currently, there are three main groups of Jews in Azerbaijan. These groups include European Jews (also known as Ashkenazi), Mountain Jews, and Georgian Jews. Among these Jewish communities, the Mountain Jews are the oldest group.

The Mountain Jews have been settled in our country since ancient times. They primarily settled in the Derbent area (in Dagestan) and also in the Quba region. In Israel, they are referred to as both Mountain Jews and Caucasus Jews. There are different opinions about the naming of The Mountain Jews. As we know, in the 19th century, the Russians invaded the South Caucasus. They encountered the Mountain Jews, who often dressed with distinctive attire and belts. The Russians were surprised by them and called them "Mountain Jews" - "Горские евреи." When focusing on historical sources, the bravery of the Mountain Jews in battles draws attention [5].

If currently, we were to consider the entire Jewish diaspora, it becomes evident that among these diasporas, the Mountain Jews form a significant majority. The language of the Mountain Jews is Juhuri, known as such among themselves. This is the native language of the "Mountain Jews" living in Azerbaijan.

Other ethnic and minority groups residing in Azerbaijan have historically been treated by Azerbaijanis with great kindness, peacefulness, and tolerance, and

the same attitude has been extended towards the Jews. Their language, religion, customs, and traditions have been treated with particular respect by Azerbaijanis.

The year 1918 saw the Armenian Dashnaks and other Armenian militant groups perpetrate ruthless massacres against Azerbaijanis on Azerbaijani territory. During the same year, these hateful Armenian Dashnaks and other militant groups committed severe atrocities against the Mountain Jews in Azerbaijan. The brutal massacres committed by Armenian Dashnaks and other militant groups against the Jews were not confined solely to the Quba region but extended to other areas of Azerbaijan. As a result of these actions, up to 3,000 Jews were killed, leaving a grim mark in history. In addition to massacring Azerbaijanis, these Armenian Dashnak militant groups also murdered peaceful Jews who had refused to collaborate with Armenians as a result of the genocide carried out in Azerbaijan's territory [8].

Azerbaijan, renowned for its multicultural and tolerant values, stands as one of the foremost countries globally due to its ethnic and religious diversity. This diversity in ethnicity and religion has historically been prevalent in our country. Historical records suggest that the period of the Sasanian Empire coincides with the V-VI centuries. Based on some accounts, the settlement of Mountain Jews, namely, in northern Azerbaijani territories, aligns with the era of the Sasanian Empire, particularly in the V-VI centuries. Similarly, according to some hypotheses, the ancestors of the Mountain Jews migrated from Mesopotamia during the V-VI centuries, crossing two major rivers, the Tigris and Euphrates, and settled in the Eastern Caucasus [8].

It's known from history that pogroms against Jews occurred in several regions of the Russian Empire. As a result of these pogroms in the territories of the Russian Empire, many Ashkenazi Jews sought refuge in our country, the Land of Fires, Azerbaijan. The Ashkenazi Jewish ethnic subgroup settled primarily in the capital city, Baku. It appears that to escape these persecutions, this Jewish community, the Ashkenazim, turned to our country, Azerbaijan, considering our Republic their second homeland.

As we know, in the 19th and 20th centuries, Azerbaijan's multiculturalism evolved: the number of ethnic groups and minority populations increased, contributing to the diversity of our country's multicultural group. New ethnic groups like Russians and Germans became part of Azerbaijan's multiculturalism. Their inclusion enriched Azerbaijan's longstanding Eastern-rooted multiculturalism with Western hues. Additionally, both Germans and Russians brought their cultures, religions, languages, and customs to our country's social life.

Academician Kamal Abdullayev, a genuine member of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, an Advisor on national issues, the Head of the Supervisory Board of the Baku International Multiculturalism Center, a prominent writer, and the rector of Azerbaijan Languages University, has emphasized that historical conditions that have shaped Azerbaijan, notably the Eldiguzids lineage (Atabegs) dating back to the Caucasian Albania period, the Safavids (from December 22, 1501, to March 8, 1736), the Afshars, the Qajars, and

even the era of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, collectively represent a rich, magnificent political legacy. National Leader Heydar Aliyev profoundly emphasized the crucial and vital significance of multiculturalism values and tolerant attitudes for the Republic of Azerbaijan on numerous occasions, fully acknowledging their exceptional importance [1].

The Republic of Azerbaijan's multicultural and tolerant values are safeguarded by the state. The most crucial figure in this regard was the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev. Under his direction and initiatives, this matter found full expression in legal documents, notably in the Constitution. For instance, Article 25, paragraph 3 of Azerbaijan's Constitution guarantees the "right to equality," Article 44, paragraph 1 guarantees the "right to national identity," Article 45, paragraphs 1 and 2 ensure the "right to use one's native language," and there are various other articles within the Constitution that exemplify these principles.

At such a time, being recognized as a haven of stability for the Republic of Azerbaijan is highly commendable. This recognition naturally fosters positive perceptions in the global community. All these positive aspects are related to the successes achieved by our country in the fields of tolerance and multiculturalism. The national leader Heydar Aliyev emphasized the special importance and value of these multicultural and tolerant values, stating that by uniting more of the country's people, the state becomes richer, and each of these nations contributes its own gift to world civilization [2].

As we emphasize, regardless of their religion and ethnicity, all citizens living in the Republic of Azerbaijan enjoy equal rights, possess the same rights, and, most importantly, these rights of citizens are protected and preserved under the relevant laws. Decisions have been made by our state to ensure that these citizens can freely express their religious beliefs. The inclusion of the 'Freedom of Religious Beliefs' law in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan is a clear example of this.

The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, continues with great dedication along the path set by his esteemed political predecessor. The President of Azerbaijan declares to the whole world that multiculturalism is a state policy in Azerbaijan and emphasizes that it has no alternative. President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, has repeatedly highlighted that multiculturalism has deep historical roots in Azerbaijan and has underscored the ordinary lifestyle of the Azerbaijani people, who possess a rich culture [4].

President Ilham Aliyev has stated that our main goal is to contribute to the development of multicultural societies and to showcase our positive experience to the world because the experience gained in the Republic of Azerbaijan is positive in this field.

One of the fundamental directions of President Ilham Aliyev's policy is to promote the multicultural and tolerant values that have been characteristic of the Azerbaijani people for centuries to the entire world. President Ilham Aliyev has recognized Azerbaijani multiculturalism as a state policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. He has also evaluated Azerbaijani multi-

culturalism as a lifestyle of the Azerbaijani people. Giving value to this policy as a state policy, the President attaches special importance to collaborating with international organizations in its implementation. President Aliyev emphasizes the importance of joining conventions related to the protection of the rights and freedoms of national minorities. One significant step in the policy of multiculturalism, which President Ilham Aliyev values as a state policy, is the establishment of the Baku International Multiculturalism Center [4].

Conclusion

In Azerbaijan today, ethnic groups living in the country have the right to speak and write in their own languages. At the same time, newspapers and journals are published, and radio and television channels operate in the languages of national minorities living in Azerbaijan. Lessons are conducted in schools in the Talysh, the Avar and the Lezgian languages. Teaching is carried out in Russian in more than 300 schools.

Compared to the international world and the developed world countries, in the Republic of Azerbaijan, witnessed development of multicultural and tolerant values at a very high level, extensively, and has been elevated to the State level in a genuinely positive form of State policy. In European culture, multiculturalism remains merely a subject for discussion, where debates find their place, but rarely materialize into action.

The way we see it, the defense and protection of freedoms of national minorities in Azerbaijan are at the state level. This commendable policy developing at the state level sets an unparalleled example for nations worldwide. And this, in the truest sense of the word, is a very proud state of affairs.

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